

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

DMP: Analysis of PFAS Fate and Transport in the Upper Danube [PFAS_UDB]

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	Meiqi Liu
Version:	1.0
Status:	Published
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14254132

DMP: Analysis of PFAS Fate and Transport in the Upper Danube has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the DMP: Analysis of PFAS Fate and Transport in the Upper Danube project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by parties of the DMP: Analysis of PFAS Fate and Transport in the Upper Danube project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The DMP: Analysis of PFAS Fate and Transport in the Upper Danube project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No [XXXXX].

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From:	Meiqi Liu	Creator/manager	01.12.2024
Moderated by:			
Reviewed by:			
Approved by:			

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	[01.12.2024]	Document created	Meiqi Liu

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

Content

1. Executive Summary	5
1.1. Introduction	5
1.2. Data Summary	5
1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse	7
1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users:	7
2. FAIR data	7
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	7
2.2. Making data accessible	8
2.3. Making data interoperable	10
2.4. Increase data re-use	11
3. Other research outputs	11
4. Allocation of resources	12
5. Data security	12
5.1. Storage and backup facilities	12
5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data	13
5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data	14
6. Ethical and legal issues	15
6.1. Personal data	15
6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership	15
6.3. Ethical issues	15
7. Other issues	15

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Meiqi Liu (meiqi.liu@tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Analysis and Visualization Toolkit for PFAS Data at Upper Danube	Source code		100 MB	no
P2	Analysis Results and Maps for PFAS concentrations at Upper Danube	Images		100 MB	no
P3	Comparative assessment of PFAS concentrations in emission pathways, surface and groundwater in the upper Danube Basin	Standard office documents		100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P4	PFAS-Belastungen im Einzugsgebiet der oberen Donau	Standard office documents		100 MB	no
P5	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) Concentrations in the Upper Danube Catchment: Integrated Dataset from H2020 Project PROMISCES - Case Study 2	Databases, Archived data		100 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source
R1	Inventory of hazardous substance concentrations in different environmental compartments in the Danube river basin Output of Danube Hazard m ³ c, an Interreg project in the Danube Transnational Programm	10.48436/xwve4-h7v43
R2	Austria National Groundwater Survey Data	https://info.bml.gv.at/themen/wasser/wasser-oesterreich/wasserrecht_national/planung/GZUEV.html

R3	FATERISK Aqua Project PFAS data	https://www.tuwien.at/en/cee/iwr/water/projects/ongoing-projects/faterisk-aq
R4	NaWas-Raab project PFAS data	https://www.tuwien.at/en/cee/iwr/water/projects/ongoing-projects/nawas-raa
R5	"Heat below the city" Project PFAS data	https://www.wwf.at/funding/programmes/esr/ESR20-040/
R6	PFAS monitoring data at Vorarlberg	https://vorarlberg.at/documents/302033/844659/PFAS_in_Vorarlberg.pdf/c030cf69-29ef-4b5c-c91a73ca8804?t=1623823252212

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Concentration data on selected PFASs and within the study area of this project (Upper Danube) will be added to the SQL database we prepared for this project, with proper data cleaning and treatment (e.g. unit conversion, metadata preservation and naming conversion) using R code.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention. Timestamp is automatically updated when new record is uploaded. Version control is automated.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide README files with explanations at project and dataset level. For detailed chemical substances, the dataset refer to its records at several scientific naming systems: (1) NORMAN Database System (<https://www.norman-network.com/nds/>)

(2) CAS Registry number (<https://www.cas.org/cas-data/cas-registry>). This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-12-04	GitHub		GPL-3.0-or-later
P2	Open		2024-12-04	GitHub		GPL-3.0-or-later
P3	Open		2023-04-23	Zenodo		CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2023-07-24	Zenodo		CC-BY-4.0
P5	Restricted		2025-04-29	Zenodo, TU Wien Research Data		CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to

funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Microsoft License needed to open the database in .acddb format, but information will also be provided under same structure in .csv

PC equipped with R-4.4.0 or higher to process the code.

Description of protocol to access restricted data: This dataset is currently under embargo to allow for the completion and peer review of a related research publication. Full access to the dataset will be granted following the acceptance and publication of the associated paper, ensuring the integrity and originality of the research findings. During the embargo period, access may be granted upon request for collaborative or verification purposes, subject to approval by the dataset authors.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

A Gitlab project page will be publicly available for clone all necessary codes in reproducing data analysis. Both Gitlab project and Dataset itself has license with proper data re-use permissions.

The following data quality checks will be done: calibration, repeated samples or measurements, standardised data capture, data entry validation, peer review of data, and representation with controlled vocabularies.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR as outlined below.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Staff operating costs	Personnel	Personnel cost for creating/maintaining the data.	EUR	2.000
Estimated total costs				2.000

Coverage of costs:

...

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [Matthias Zessner-Spitzenberg \(matthias.zessner-spitzenberg@tuwien.ac.at\)](mailto:matthias.zessner-spitzenberg@tuwien.ac.at) being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

P1 (Analysis and Visualization Toolkit for PFAS Data at Upper Danube), P2 (Analysis Results and Maps for PFAS concentrations at Upper Danube) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by TU.it. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

R1 (Inventory of hazardous substance concentrations in different environmental compartments in the Danube river basin Output of Danube Hazard m³c, an Interreg project in the Danube Transnational Programm), R2 (Austria National Groundwater Survey Data), R3 (FATERISK Aqua Project PFAS data), R4 (NaWas-Raab project PFAS data), R5 ("Heat below the city" Project PFAS data), R6 (PFAS monitoring data at Vorarlberg) will be stored on Server Housing: With this service provided by TU.it, the server is housed in a dedicated TU.it server room with limited access and operated by our institute.

R1 (Inventory of hazardous substance concentrations in different environmental compartments in the Danube river basin Output of Danube Hazard m³c, an Interreg project in the Danube Transnational Programm), P5 (Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) Concentrations in the Upper Danube Catchment: Integrated Dataset from H2020 Project PROMISCES - Case Study 2) will be stored on TUhost: TUhost is a central and highly available TU.it virtualisation platform, hosted on VMware. Hardware, storage, and backup will be provided by TU.it and our institute will be responsible for the server operation.

P3 (Comparative assessment of PFAS concentrations in emission pathways, surface and groundwater in the upper Danube Basin), P4 (PFAS-Belastungen im Einzugsgebiet der oberen Donau), P5 (Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) Concentrations in the Upper Danube Catchment: Integrated Dataset from H2020 Project PROMISCES - Case Study 2) will be stored on Zenodo. External storage will be used because project requirements (by european commission).

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	writing
P2	reading only	reading only	reading only
P3	reading only	reading only	reading only
P4	reading only	reading only	reading only
P5	reading only	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	no access
R4	reading only	reading only	no access
R5	reading only	reading only	no access
R6	reading only	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub	10 years
P2	GitHub	10 years
P3	Zenodo	10 years
P4	Zenodo	25 years
P5	Zenodo, TU Wien Research Data	100 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?